

Narratives of allophilia and belonging among international university students

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Publication of the International Society of Psychology, Counselling and Education

Understanding how international university students develop a sense of belonging within host universities is central to creating inclusive academic environments. While allophilia has been examined in various cultural contexts, little is known about how international university students experience positive intergroup relations within Philippine higher education. This study employed a qualitative narrative research design to explore how international university students in Metro Manila experienced allophilia, defined as positive attitudes and behaviours directed towards outgroup members. Semi structured interviews were conducted with four international university students enrolled in universities in Metro Manila, and the narratives were analysed using thematic analysis to examine patterns of meaning making and adjustment. The findings revealed a staged process of integration characterised by four phases: Discovery, Adaptation, Breaking, and Maturation. Across these phases, experiences of acceptance, peer support, and positive engagement with faculty played a critical role in shaping students' sense of belonging, while language barriers and cultural differences emerged as recurring challenges. By foregrounding positive intergroup experiences rather than deficit-based accounts of discrimination, this study extends allophilia research into a Southeast Asian academic context and contributes to a more nuanced understanding of belonging as a dynamic and relational process within international higher education.

Keywords: belonging; cross cultural interaction; foreign students; intergroup relations; qualitative narratives

Allophilia refers to positive feelings, attitudes, and behaviours directed towards individuals or groups perceived as different from oneself (Devine, 2005; Legault et al., 2025; Shnabel & Ullrich, 2025). Unlike constructs that centre on prejudice, xenophobia, or discrimination, allophilia emphasises genuine appreciation, respect, and positive engagement with diversity (Ertorer, 2024). Within intergroup relations research, this concept represents a shift away from deficit-oriented frameworks that focus primarily on reducing negative attitudes, towards a strengths-based perspective that examines how positive intergroup relations are actively formed and sustained (Dwyer, 2022). Rather than treating tolerance as the endpoint of social cohesion, allophilia foregrounds the conditions under which affirming and meaningful relationships between groups can develop.

The concept was further articulated by Pittinsky (2005), who described allophilia as the “liking or love of the other” and argued that reducing prejudice alone is insufficient for achieving social harmony. From this perspective, the absence of hostility does not necessarily translate into inclusion or belonging. Instead, Pittinsky emphasised the importance of fostering positive intergroup orientations such as affection, comfort, engagement, enthusiasm, and a sense of kinship, which he viewed as central to deeper and more enduring intergroup relationships. This framing expands the scope of intergroup research by positioning positive attitudes not as secondary outcomes, but as core mechanisms through which inclusive social environments are created.

In an increasingly globalised world, advances in communication and mobility have intensified cross cultural interactions, particularly within higher education institutions that host students from diverse national and cultural backgrounds (Bai et al., 2024; Bakay, 2023; Knight, 2004). Universities are now key sites of intercultural contact, where international university students are required to navigate unfamiliar academic norms, social expectations, and cultural practices. As higher education continues to internationalise, understanding the experiences of international university students and the factors that shape their integration and sense of belonging has become essential to fostering inclusive academic environments (Brito et al., 2025; Hurtado & Carter, 1997; Tavares, 2024). Research consistently shows that belonging is closely linked to academic engagement, persistence, and psychological well-being (Bautista et al., 2018), yet the processes through which belonging develops remain unevenly understood across institutional and cultural contexts (Allen et al., 2024; Graham & Moir, 2022; Yi et al., 2024).

Within the Philippine context, intergroup relations are shaped by a complex historical legacy rooted in colonial experiences, which continue to influence contemporary social dynamics (Lodangco, 2023). While existing research in this context has largely focused on discrimination, bias, and marginalisation, comparatively little attention has been given to positive intergroup experiences, particularly from the perspective of outgroup members. This emphasis on deficit-based accounts has limited understanding of how acceptance, welcome, and positive regard are experienced by international university students within Philippine universities. Allophilia offers a useful framework for examining these positive encounters and addressing this gap in the literature.

Operationally, allophilia in this study is defined as the experience of acceptance, welcome, and positive regard received from a group to which one does not belong (Gillham et al., 2011). Using a qualitative narrative research design, this study explores the lived experiences of international university students studying in universities within Metro Manila, Philippines. Data were collected through semi structured interviews to examine how international university students experience allophilia in academic settings and how these experiences influence their sense of belonging. The study addressed the central research question: What narratives do international university students share regarding their experiences of allophilia in the school context? By foregrounding positive intergroup relations, this research contributes to the literature on inclusivity in higher education and illustrates the role of allophilia in fostering welcoming and supportive learning environments.

METHODOLOGY

Design

This study adopted a qualitative narrative research design to examine how international university students experience allophilia within Philippine higher education. Narrative inquiry was selected to capture how participants constructed meaning around their experiences of acceptance, belonging, and adjustment over time, rather than to compare cases or generate generalisable claims. Semi structured interviews were used to allow participants to reflect on their academic, social, and cultural experiences in their own words, while still providing sufficient structure to ensure alignment with the study's aims.

Participants and study site

Participants were four international university students enrolled in higher education institutions within Metro Manila, Philippines. They varied in nationality, year level, and length of residence in the country, allowing for diverse perspectives on adjustment and belonging within the same sociocultural context. The small sample size was considered appropriate given the narrative design and the study's focus on depth of experience rather than breadth or representativeness.

Sampling and recruitment

Purposive sampling was employed to identify participants who met the inclusion criteria relevant to the study's conceptual focus. Eligible participants were international university students currently enrolled in a Philippine university who reported experiences of positive interaction, acceptance, or support from members of the host community. To support the selection process, a brief screening tool adapted from the Allophilia Scale developed by Pittinsky et al. (2011) was administered via Google Forms. The adapted tool was used solely for screening purposes to ensure conceptual alignment with allophilia and was not used as a quantitative outcome measure. Participants who achieved a minimum score of 60% on indicators related to perceived acceptance, respect, comfort, and desire for social connection were invited to participate in the interview phase.

Data collection procedure

Data were collected through individual semi structured interviews conducted in English. Interviews focused on participants' experiences of adjusting to academic life, interactions with peers and faculty, perceived acceptance or exclusion, and the ways these experiences shaped their sense of belonging. Open ended questions were used, with follow up probes to encourage elaboration and reflection. All interviews were audio recorded with participants' consent and later transcribed verbatim for analysis.

Data analysis

Data analysis was conducted using thematic analysis as the primary analytic method. This approach was chosen to systematically identify recurring patterns and shared meanings across participants' narratives while remaining sensitive to individual context and interpretation. Transcripts were read repeatedly to achieve familiarity with the data, followed by initial coding to capture salient features related to experiences of allophilia, adjustment, and belonging. Codes were then reviewed and organised into broader themes that reflected common narrative patterns across participants.

Kelly's Repertory Grid was used as a supplementary interpretive framework during the analytic process. Rather than functioning as a separate analytic method, it supported the examination of how participants constructed personal meanings around their experiences, particularly in relation to acceptance, challenge, and adaptation. This combined approach allowed for structured theme development while retaining attention to individual meaning making processes.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was obtained prior to data collection. All participants provided informed consent through a Google Form before taking part in the study. Participation was voluntary, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any stage without penalty. To protect confidentiality, identifying information was minimised, and pseudonyms were used in all transcripts and reporting. Participants were informed that interviews would be audio recorded and that anonymised findings were intended for publication and potential online access. Interview questions were designed to minimise discomfort, and participants were free to decline to answer any question they found distressing.

RESULTS

The data were analysed using thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns across participants' narratives. Four interrelated themes emerged, reflecting a temporal process through which international university students described their experiences of acceptance, challenge, and belonging while studying in Philippine universities. These themes were labelled the Discovery Period, Adaptation Period, Breaking Period, and Maturation Period. Together, they represent successive phases in participants' adjustment journeys rather than discrete or isolated experiences. Participant quotations are included to illustrate each theme and are identified using participant codes (P1–P4).

Theme 1: Discovery Period (A New Beginning)

The Discovery Period captured participants' early experiences upon arriving in the Philippines and entering their respective universities. This phase was characterised by anticipation, curiosity, and uncertainty, alongside initial encounters with academic systems, social environments, and cultural differences. Participants described this period as one of orientation, during which first impressions played a significant role in shaping expectations of belonging.

Several participants reported feeling unexpectedly welcomed during their initial weeks. One participant reflected that classmates were "very kind and very welcoming, especially in this school" (P1). Another described how peers actively supported their adjustment, stating that classmates were "extra welcoming" and helped keep them informed about academic matters (P2).

Despite these positive encounters, participants also described early confusion and uncertainty. One participant explained, "I had difficulty mingling at first. I didn't know which was my section or who my classmates were" (P3). Another participant linked their decision to study abroad to limited exposure to other cultures in their home country, noting, "Most people don't really know how to speak English, so I wanted to try studying in another country" (P4). These early experiences laid the groundwork for how participants approached social interaction and adjustment in subsequent phases.

Theme 2: Adaptation Period (Traversing the Unfamiliar)

The Adaptation Period reflected participants' gradual adjustment to academic routines, cultural norms, and social relationships. During this phase, international university students described increasing familiarity with their surroundings and greater confidence in engaging with peers and faculty.

Forming friendships was central to this stage. One participant stated that "making friends was pretty easy, even on my first day of school" (P2), while another noted, "It felt like they were the ones who adjusted to me. My classmates were really kind" (P4). These interactions contributed to growing feelings of interpersonal belonging.

Participants also described adapting to practical and environmental differences, including daily schedules, climate, and language use. One participant commented, "I couldn't get used to the schedule and especially the heat" (P1). Language barriers were also prominent, with one participant explaining, "At first, I could only answer yes or no because I couldn't speak Tagalog" (P4).

Support from peers, faculty, and staff featured strongly during this phase. Participants described receiving encouragement and assistance that reinforced feelings of inclusion. One participant noted, "That was the moment I felt this is the place I want to be. People kept encouraging me, and I felt welcomed" (P1).

Theme 3: Breaking Period (Exploring the Negatives)

The Breaking Period encompassed experiences that disrupted participants' growing sense of comfort and belonging. This phase was marked by frustration, exclusion, and heightened awareness of difference, particularly in relation to language use and social positioning.

Language barriers emerged as a significant challenge. One participant explained that when conversations shifted to Tagalog, they "felt left out" (P1). Another expressed concern about classroom instruction, stating, "Professors should speak English more because that's how international university students fail or get bad grades" (P2). These experiences affected both academic participation and confidence.

Participants also described moments of social vulnerability linked to their status as international university students. One participant reflected, "Sometimes people try to take advantage because I'm from another country, especially when it comes to money" (P2). Another shared an earlier thought about separation as a possible solution, stating, "I used to think there should be a separate facility for international university students because communicating is really hard" (P1).

Although challenging, participants did not describe this phase as entirely negative. Instead, it was often framed as a period that prompted reflection and adjustment, highlighting the ongoing effort required to sustain a sense of belonging.

Theme 4: Maturation Period (Mastery Over the New Environment)

The Maturation Period reflected participants' accounts of increased confidence, independence, and emotional stability. By this stage, international university students described feeling more settled within their academic and social environments and better equipped to manage earlier challenges.

Participants reported personal growth and increased self-reliance. One participant stated, "At first, I was challenged, but over time I learned to be more independent. I gained friendships and felt

comfortable in the school” (P3). Another described adopting an attitude of openness as a coping strategy, noting, “I just accept and understand. That’s how I adjust here in the Philippines” (P4). This phase was associated with a strengthened sense of belonging and integration. Participants described feeling accepted within the university community and expressed appreciation for the relationships they had developed with peers, faculty, and staff. The Maturation Period represented the culmination of earlier experiences, in which moments of acceptance, challenge, and adaptation collectively shaped a more stable sense of belonging.

DISCUSSION

This study examined how international university students studying in Metro Manila experienced allophilia and developed a sense of belonging within Philippine higher education. The findings suggest that belonging is not a fixed or immediate outcome of internationalisation, but a dynamic and negotiated process shaped by interpersonal encounters, institutional practices, and contextual challenges (Gilani & Thomas, 2025). The four analytically derived phases Discovery, Adaptation, Breaking, and Maturation offer a process-oriented framework for understanding how positive intergroup relations unfold over time alongside moments of disruption and uncertainty.

The Discovery phase highlights the significance of early interpersonal encounters in shaping international university students’ expectations of inclusion. Participants’ accounts indicate that initial experiences of welcome and openness contributed to early feelings of acceptance, even as students navigated unfamiliar academic systems and social norms. From an allophilia perspective, these early interactions reflect positive orientations towards outgroup members that go beyond mere tolerance (Vezzali et al., 2023). At the same time, the coexistence of warmth and disorientation underscores that positive affect alone is insufficient to produce immediate belonging. Rather, belonging emerged as tentative and provisional, shaped through ongoing interaction rather than first impressions alone (Crawford et al., 2023).

As students moved into the Adaptation phase, belonging became increasingly embedded in everyday academic and social practices. Peer relationships and supportive engagement with faculty and staff functioned as key relational anchors, enabling students to manage cultural differences, academic expectations, and practical challenges (Dias Broens et al., 2024; Gilani & Thomas, 2025; Ranabahu & De Silva, 2024). Notably, several participants described experiences in which local students and institutional actors adjusted around them, rather than positioning adaptation as a one-sided responsibility. This finding complicates dominant adjustment models that frame international students as passive recipients of host culture norms (Ranabahu & De Silva, 2024). Viewed through the lens of allophilia, reciprocal adjustment represents an active form of positive intergroup engagement in which difference is accommodated rather than erased (Vezzali et al., 2023).

The Breaking phase introduces an important counterpoint to idealised narratives of inclusion. Experiences of language related exclusion, perceived inequity, and vulnerability disrupted earlier feelings of stability and exposed structural and symbolic boundaries within the academic environment (Dias Broens et al., 2024; Ennin & Manariyo, 2023; Tekin & Trofimovich, 2024). These moments demonstrate that positive intergroup orientations operate within existing power relations rather than transcending them. Crucially, participants did not describe these experiences as negating earlier acceptance but as revealing the conditional and context dependent nature of belonging, highlighting how inclusion and exclusion can coexist within the same institutional space (Crawford et al., 2023).

The Maturation phase reflects how international university students integrated earlier experiences into a more stable sense of belonging and self positioning. By this stage, participants described

increased confidence and emotional resilience, suggesting that belonging was no longer reliant on constant affirmation or exceptional treatment. Rather than signalling the absence of challenge, maturation involved reframing difficulties as manageable aspects of daily academic life. From an allophilia standpoint, this phase aligns with evidence that sustained intergroup contact fosters enduring positive orientations when interactions become routine rather than exceptional (Vezzali et al., 2023).

The findings extend existing literature on international university students by conceptualising belonging as a process shaped through time, interaction, and context rather than as a discrete outcome of successful adjustment (Crawford et al., 2023; Dias Broens et al., 2024; Gilani & Thomas, 2025). While much research on internationalisation has focused on barriers, stressors, and deficit-based accounts of adaptation, this study foregrounds positive intergroup experiences while acknowledging moments of rupture and constraint. In doing so, it offers a more nuanced account of belonging that recognises the relational labour involved in sustaining inclusion within higher education settings (Gilani & Thomas, 2025).

The phase-based framework developed in this study contributes to allophilia research by demonstrating how positive intergroup orientations are enacted, challenged, and renegotiated within everyday academic life. Situated within a Southeast Asian context that remains underrepresented in the literature, the findings highlight the value of examining allophilia beyond Western institutional settings (Ranabahu & De Silva, 2024). More broadly, the study reinforces the need to conceptualise internationalisation not only as a structural or demographic phenomenon but as a lived relational process through which belonging is continually produced and contested (Gilani & Thomas, 2025).

CONCLUSION

This study examined how international university students studying in the Philippines experienced acceptance, connection, and belonging within a new academic and cultural environment. By foregrounding students' narratives, the research demonstrates that belonging was not experienced as an immediate or stable condition, but as something gradually shaped through interaction, challenge, and adaptation over time. The four phases identified Discovery, Adaptation, Breaking, and Maturation capture this process as lived and negotiated, rather than as a linear pathway or predetermined outcome.

The findings highlight the emotional and relational complexity of international university students' adjustment experiences. Early moments of welcome and openness were meaningful in shaping initial perceptions of inclusion, but they did not in themselves secure lasting belonging. Instead, belonging emerged through sustained engagement with peers, faculty, and institutional contexts, while remaining vulnerable to disruption through language barriers, perceived inequities, and moments of exclusion. These difficulties did not negate positive experiences but became part of the broader process through which students developed resilience, confidence, and a more secure sense of place within the university community.

By approaching these experiences through the lens of allophilia, the study contributes to a more balanced understanding of belonging that moves beyond deficit-based accounts focused solely on stress, marginalisation, or failure to adapt. Rather than positioning belonging as the endpoint of successful adjustment, the findings emphasise its ongoing and relational nature, shaped by everyday intergroup encounters and contextual conditions. The phase-based framework advanced here offers a conceptual lens for understanding how positive intergroup orientations are enacted, challenged, and sustained within higher education settings.

At the same time, the findings reflect narratives drawn from a specific institutional and cultural context and from a small group of participants whose accounts prioritise depth over breadth. As such, the study does not seek to offer generalisable claims, but to illuminate processes through which belonging is experienced and negotiated. Experiences of allophilia and belonging may take different forms across institutions, regions, and student populations, underscoring the value of continued qualitative inquiry into international university students' lived experiences across diverse educational contexts.

This study underscores that belonging in higher education is neither guaranteed nor static, but continually produced through interaction, negotiation, and time. By attending to both moments of connection and rupture, it contributes to a more nuanced and contextually grounded understanding of how international university students experience inclusion within contemporary higher education.

Acknowledgements: The researchers sincerely thank Professor Jim Harter Casibua and Julienne Eunice Palmones for their role as validators and extend heartfelt appreciation to all participants for their valuable time and contributions.

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: New Era University

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